

Grain quality

Multisample rice cooker for evaluating eating quality

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Preparing cooked rice of several varieties or breeding lines to evaluate their eating quality characteristics is a difficult task. The error across samples is often high because each test entry must be cooked separately, usually at different times and using different apparatuses. To reduce this error, we developed a special cooker that uses indirect heat through water to subject the samples to the same conditions (see figure). One unit can cook nine samples simultaneously. This cooker may also be used to test the quality of small samples or samples from a single plant.

Grains and the appropriate amount of water are placed in the cooking cup. The base pan is filled with water to provide indirect heat for cooking. Cooking is done in two stages: first with water in the base pan for 20 min, then by removing the water and applying direct heat to the rice cups for 5 min. With two units, the cooking process of many samples can be continuous, with one having water in the base pan and the other without. About 120 samples can be evaluated in 1 d using two units. ■

Multisample rice cooker.

Njavara: a unique rice race of the humid tropics

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Njavara is a unique land race of rice valued for its medicinal properties. It is used in treating circulatory, respiratory, and digestive ailments in ayurvedic medicine.

We conducted an experiment to investigate the types of amino acids and the amounts of each in Njavara grain of the black-glumed and golden-glumed grain types grown under rainfed upland and lowland cropping situations compared with the commonly grown traditional variety PTB20 during 1994-96 (see table). The black-glumed type had 192% more free amino acid content and the golden-glumed type 16% more than that of

PTB20 grown in the lowlands. The land race's medicinal property appears to be attributable to the sulfur-containing amino acid, methionine, which is involved in the metabolic pathway of the biosynthesis of thiamine (Vitamin B₁), the deficiency of which causes beriberi. Black-glumed Njavara is richer than pulses in free amino acid content, entitling it to be called a proteinaceous cereal. ■

Total free amino acid content and some probable amino acids present in Njavara as compared with PTB20 grain.

Condition	Duration (d)	Amino acids identified	Total free amino acid content (mg g ⁻¹)
<i>Black-glumed Njavara</i>			
Wetland	99	DL-2-amino-N-butyric acid and DL-isoleucine	0.316
Open upland	94	L-histidine monohydrochloride, L-leucine, DL-methionine and L-proline	0.670
50-70% shaded upland	93	DL-2-amino-N-butyric acid, L-cysteine hydrochloride monohydrate, DL-methionine and DL-isoleucine	0.814
20-40% shaded upland	93	DL-threonine, DL-methionine and L-leucine	0.334
<i>Golden yellow-glumed Njavara</i>			
Wetland	103	L-histidine monochloride, L-ornithine monohydrochloride and DL-isoleucine	0.089
Open upland	95	DL-2-amino-N-butyric acid, L-proline, DL-methionine and L-leucine	0.424
50-70% shaded upland	102	DL-threonine, DL-methionine and DL-isoleucine	0.169
20-40% shaded upland	99	DL-threonine, DL-methionine and L-leucine	0.164
PTB20 in wetland situation	120	DL-serine	0.183

Seven promising breeding lines of the F₈ generation were studied for stability to pest resistance and agronomic characters during the 1993-95 monsoon seasons. In the field, 30-d-old seedlings of these test lines were transplanted at 10- × 20- cm spacing in two 2-m rows along with checks TN1 (susceptible) and Ptb33 (resistant). At maximum tillering stage, all plants were inoculated with Xoo by clip inoculation method. Recommended agronomic practices were followed to raise the crop. Observations were recorded for all hills 50 d after transplanting when gall midge incidence peaked. Likewise BLB-inoculated plants were observed for disease symptoms at maximum disease pressure.

At harvest, grain was collected for re-sowing the next wet season. Grain and plant characters were also recorded. In the glasshouse, these lines were screened against *N. lugens*; feeding and probing mark studies were also carried out.

Except for pureline IET6286, all seven breeding lines were derived from a widely cultivated variety Ruchi, which is resistant to gall midge and moderately resistant to BLB (Table 1). IR64 is resistant to the Raipur BPH insect population. RM1 (Raipur mutant), also used as a donor, is resistant to BLB but susceptible to gall midge. IR19661-23-3-2 and IR27325-111-2-1 are gall midge-susceptible but

Pest resistance

New rice breeding lines with multiple pest resistance

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Brown planthopper (BPH) (*Nilaparvata lugens*), gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*), and

bacterial leaf blight (BLB) disease (*Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* [Xoo]) are widespread in the Chhattisgarh region of Madhya Pradesh. To overcome this major constraint to selecting proper varieties in the integrated pest management program, we sought to develop new breeding lines with multiple pest resistance.

Table 1. Agronomic characters of advanced breeding lines.

Breeding line	Parentage	Test weight (g) 1,000 seed	Duration (d)	Hull color	Kernel color	Grain dimension ^a	Plant type ^b	Plant color
R712-1-65-1-1	Ruchi/IR19661-23-3-2	33	125	Light golden	White	LS	SD	Green
R710-3-37-1-1-1	Ruchi/IR27325-111-2-1	31	125	Light golden	White	LS	SD	Green
IET6286	-	23	155	Deep golden	White	LS	T	Green
R746-2-34-1-2-1	IR64/Ruchi	24	125	Straw	White	LS	SD	Green
R714-2-9-3-2-2	RMI/Ruchi	28	125	Straw	White	LS	SD	Purple
R714-1-19-1-5-1	RMI/Ruchi	27	125	Straw	White	LS	SD	Purple
R720-1-91-2-1-1	Ruchi/RM1	26	130	Straw	White	LS	SD	Purple
R714-3-103-1-3-2	RMI/Ruchi	31	128	Light golden	White	LS	ST	Purple ring in green plant
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	23	120	Straw	White	MS	D	Green
PTB 33 (resistant check for BPH and BLB)	-	18	185	Straw	White	LS	T	Green

^aLS = long slender, MS = medium slender. ^bSD = semidwarf, T = tall, D = dwarf.